

TEACHING ENGLISH THROUGH ROLE-PLAYING

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Annotation: This article is dedicated to the importance of role playing in teaching the English language to upper intermediate level learners. The most important issues needed for the organization of role play activities are looked through. The article also describes the author's comments based on the method of observation and experience in teaching. Recommendations for the targeted organization of role playing games are given.

Keywords: role play, learning environment, drama activity, collaborative learning, interaction.

INTRODUCTION

English as a foreign language is taught at high schools, colleges, universities etc. Like any other subjects, English can be taught by a formative or the communicative approach. Throughout the completion of the article lots of materials, literature and other resources were revised by us. By investigating we aimed to know whether the scores of speaking taught by using role play better or not by comparing the students' scores before and after being taught by using role play technique, to develop learners' speaking skills through communicative language activities and games.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

We selected modern approaches and methods (through activities and games) of teaching English to students. It is used comparative method in this article.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Role play is one of the most topical subjects in modern methods of teaching English. At present most of the trained teachers of our country are teaching English using different activities and games in their classes. So, we wanted to know the learners' and teachers' perception of using these methods and approaches, how they implement communicative speaking activities and games, rather than Traditional Approach. To compensate for the limitations of the traditional language teaching methods, new ways of teaching have been introduced in EFL and ESP settings to improve learners' abilities to use English in real life situational contexts.

Using activities advocates teaching practices that develop communicative competence in authentic contexts. However, the theories and practices of CLT

have faced various challenges in EFL contexts. Thus, this study explores the effectiveness and importance of activities and games in teaching English to students, with the recommendation that their views be considered in decisions regarding the integration of CLT into our Education system. This means that success of learning a foreign language depends on how well learners have developed their communicative competences and how much they are able to apply this knowledge of language in real life situations.

To make teaching more interesting and meaningful English teachers use different types of teaching methods and approaches.

In Uzbekistan, the main focus of communicative language teaching (within activities and games) method is to help the learners/students/pupils to learn a language so that they can use it to communicate meaningfully in any real life situation. The methods assume that the learners will be able to communicate socially on an everyday basis or expert English language speakers on finance and business sphere. The communicative approach makes teachers and students consider language in terms of the communicative functions

The important advantage revealed by us is the study of language through varieties, which focus on different types of role playing activities and games, from which both teachers and language learners can benefit.

New teaching approaches through activities offer new learning strategies adding diversity and flexibility to existing methods and forms of classroom practice.

Each approach can be successfully adopted in the English language classroom either in combination with others or separately. The learners' needs are determined by learners' psychological characteristics as well as other factors influencing the learning/teaching process and it should be decisive in an approach selection. Looking through the new textbooks for learners we can notice that they are written on the base of new teaching methods especially their authors pay more attention to listening comprehension, and speaking for developing pronunciation, speech and understanding at the same time of speaking or listening through activities and games.

First of all, the article reveals that implementing role-play activities develops students' speaking skills rather than the other activities. This type of interactive activity is more appealing to the learners because they find it funny to play someone else's role. The majority of the students acknowledged that their speaking and communication skills are developed and become better as a result of continuous use of the role play activities in language learning. What is interesting, the learners told to the teacher that when they used English during

an ordinary lesson, some of them felt stressed and intimidated. The teacher also observed that when conducting the research lessons almost all of the students were really involved in the exercises.

The most interesting and enjoyable thing which attracts us more and more is that the activity seems more interesting by wearing their role costumes and make-up and make the learning process as fun for them. It was always noticeable that this helps students feel freely and helps them to improve their critical thinking abilities. Because when they act out role play activities wearing their role costumes it's noticeable that they behave themselves like real characters of their roles and enjoy doing this. Sometimes they wear the doctors', teachers', cooks', shop assistants' or the travel agent's uniform. Sometimes they try to act out the roles of some film star' or singers' roles. Surely, in order to act out their roles, they have to learn the new vocabulary closely connected with those professions. They try to do their bests to act out their roles better and better every time.

CONCLUSION

Finally, we can say that role-playing activity is a powerful and effective teaching method for learners and can be adapted to deliver any learning objectives from simple to complex concepts. In addition to this we can say that, this learning environment supports pedagogical and practical know-ledge. Furthermore, it facilitates to internalize teaching practice. The success lies in the construction and delivery with careful facilitation. It is a great method for teachers and trainers as it is an entertaining activity which makes every student be involved in the process.

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